

Appendix C – Traceability of the First Version of the MPO with the SLM

Dimensions	Subdimensions	Elements	SLM Themes
Structures	Components	Input	QP6.2
		Storage	QP6.1
		Coordination	Not confirmed
		Processing	QP6.3
		Output	QP6.3
	Contents	Projects	Not confirmed
		Thematic	QP2.1
		Observation	QP2.12
	Characteristics	Access	QP2.12
		Completeness	QP4.2
		Delimitation	Not confirmed
		Data Format	QP2.12
		Interaction	QP2.7
	Process	Data Input/Output	Collect
Storage			QP2.5
Sharing			QP2.11
Data Processing		Analysis	QP2.2
		Debate	QP3.2
		Reflection	QP2.2
		Assessment	QP2.2
		Combination	QP2.1
		Categorization	QP2.2
		View	QP2.2
		Prioritization	Not confirmed
		Prediction	QP2.2
		Validation	Not confirmed
		Coordination	QP2.6
		Collaboration	QP2.7 and QP3.2
		Follow-up	QP2.3
		Observation	QP2.12
		Whistleblowing	QP2.12
		Interaction	QP2.7 and QP3.2
		Agents	Actors
Systems	QP4.3		
Motivations	Knowledge		QP3.1
	Learning		QP3.1
	Innovation		QP3.7
	Improvement		QP3.3
	Decision Making		QP3.3
	Control		QP3.6
	Visibility		QP3.2
	Interaction		QP3.2
	Transparency		QP3.6
	Multiplication		QP3.1
	Participation		QP3.3 and QP3.6